

Impact of the Availability of Credit to Small-Scale Maize Farmers, a Case of Marondera District

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Abstract

The development of Zimbabwe's agricultural sector is facing many problems, and the lack of financial support for agriculture is an important aspect that affects its development. Therefore, improving the availability of credit for farmers is of great significance to promoting agricultural development and increasing farmers' income. Based on a field survey of farmers' credit access in Marondera District of Zimbabwe, this paper explores the factors affecting the availability of credit to maize growers in Zimbabwe and focuses on the impact of social capital towards credit. The results showed that strong social ties, the density of membership, cash contributions' index, labour contribution index, the gender of the household head and NGO intervention showed a positive impact towards access to credit. This paper, therefore, puts forward some suggestions to improve the farmers' credit access, that is, to improve the farmers' cultural level through the development of education, to carry out land reform that promotes the equity of land ownership, to increase the social capital through "knowledge resources" and "identity resources."

Keywords: Zimbabwe; Social capital; Availability of credit, small-scale maize farmers

Introduction

In Zimbabwe as in most developing countries, agriculture is said to be the backbone of the economy and its performance influences the overall standards of living of people and the level of economic development of the nation. Agriculture plays a significant role in food security as well as acting as a catalyst in economic performance and growth. It also contributes measurably towards poverty alleviation as alluded to by Malaba (2014). Nonetheless, this sector faces financial challenges which draw the hearts and attention of many researchers and agricultural economists who try to find solutions to this perpetual problem so as to strengthen the desire for high productivity and efficiency in the sector. It is clear that for the agricultural sector to be financially viable, inputs in support of credit need to be affordable, available and easily accessible to everyone in all different social classes and social groups.

Background

This paper mainly focuses on the impact of social capital on the availability of credit to maize farmers. This problem statement is a result of the decrease in the outputs of maize which is a staple cereal crop of Zimbabwe and Kapuya (2012) notes that this decrease is a result of lack of credit. By this researcher are therefore eager to know the causes of lack of credit. The role of maize remains critical to the national development agenda as the prime staple food for Zimbabwe. Food security in Zimbabwe has been and continues to be anchored on maize production although the drier regions also grow small grains which are better adapted to these areas. Currently, the nation is experiencing an unprecedented decline in maize production particularly in the smallholder farming sector (MAMID, 2010). The aggregate agriculture production index has also been on a downward trend since the year 2000 although signs of recovery have been noticed in 2011 (MoF, 2011). The downward trend in maize production has been attributed to several factors that range from macroeconomic policies, natural causes, and sector specific policies. The main reason cited for the fall in maize output has been the fall in financial assistance given usually by the government. Another reason for the drop in maize production was the fact that many farmers have been switching from the less-lucrative maize to cash crops, such as tobacco, soybeans, sunflower, groundnut and paprika as a response to payment delays for the previous year's maize crop by the Grain Marketing Board (FAO, 2014). Given the importance of the maize crop in the economy, the continuous deterioration of production has retarded the pace of economic development,

threatened the food security status and rural livelihoods of the nation. The declining performance of the maize sector has resulted in increased dependence on food imports, placing a heavy burden on the fiscus (MoF, 2010); and in some cases, recourse to food aid. The Ministry of Finance has been supporting the agricultural sector even outside the sector specific allocation on the national budget but all these efforts have not produced the desired output gains in maize production.

Moreover, Nwara (2004) alludes that one efficient way to increase grain output is by providing credit assistance to farmers. He echoes that credit is one of the critical inputs necessary for agricultural development. Kogsey (2013) observed that agricultural credit increases productivity and flourishes the standard of living of small scale farmers. As reported by Kapuya and Saruchera (2012), the maize sector seeks to increase productivity so as to reduce importation of the crop thus further reducing the input costs of the dependent industries dealing in food and feed. However, for that to happen, there is a need to understand the factors that affect the availability of credit which is mainly social capital as alluded by Aryeetey (2005).

Social capital according to Knomnga (2007) defines it generally as “relations matter”. He talks of how one interacts with the other which will lead to one or both party gaining from these relations. Moreover, there is recent evidence that social capital plays an important role in the determination of financial development. Guiso, Sapienza, and Zingales (2004) study reveal various aspects of financial development in the Italian provinces. They find that households who use cheques and invest in stocks are more likely to have access to institutional credit and use less informal credit in high social capital areas. However, Dong (2010) notes that one gets credit from informal institutions using links. Their measures of financial development are from household level surveys, while their measures of social capital are regional level variables derived from different sources. Another relevant study is that of Calderon, Chong, and Galindo (2002) who use the trust variable from the World Values Surveys to explain various measures of financial development in a cross country analysis. They found that trust is positively correlated with financial development and depth. One can clearly note that social capital plays a pivotal role in the obtainance of credit from institutions.

Forms of social capital

Social capital includes (bonding, bridging, and linking) which may improve access to credit by providing access to new and innovative information. Bonding social capital involves having ties with close family members and relatives. It is usually done with people of the same socio-economic status. Nevertheless, the strength of bridging social capital lies in enabling access to information through its connection to other networks outside one's core network. By breaking out of one's own close social circle by way of weak ties, one can access information not otherwise available (Lin 1982). The strength of linking social capital might lie in enabling access to social positions vertically higher in the social hierarchy. The higher the rank of the person with whom the ties are formed, the more useful the ties are. One can surely draw on more resources if one has rich and influential friends than if one has poor friends far from the centre of power (Lin 1999b). However, possessing a large amount of linking social capital also increases the chance of political patronage and nepotism. While this will improve access for farmers who have such connections, it will hamper access for those who do not.

Availability and access to credit

For a farmer to benefit from a formal credit lender, the size of the loan and all the applicable and necessary steps to be granted the loan, timeliness, and disbursement and repayment are most critical as stipulated by Nweze (1991). Made (2000) postulates that credit has been subsidized to a certain extent for smallholder farmers, where the interest rates are lower than those charged for large scale farmers. In the case of Zimbabwe, the Agricultural Bank of Zimbabwe is the main provider of credit to farmers and individuals belonging to the upper class because of the issue of collateral or assurance of repayment, also the credit lender provides credit to people they are connected to if they come from the underprivileged economic group as there will be assurance of repayment through the social ties they have. Also, people with closer ties to the upper-class by linking social

capital have access to this form of credit. However, Musono (2012) argues that those with the ability to access credit also are given the advantage of low interest rates. It, therefore, becomes clear that social ties facilitate credit access thereby leading in increased output was social class leads to social networks resulting in accessing credit.

In addition, credit was given through produce liberalization. The marketing of the agricultural produce was liberalized in 1990 at the inception of the Economic Structural Adjustment Programme (ESAP) in Zimbabwe. Trade liberalization in the agricultural sector then involved the reduction of government direct involvement and participation in the production, marketing and distribution of agricultural commodities. There was also removal of agricultural price controls and subsidies. The process resulted in the transformation of agricultural marketing boards into independent entities for instance co-operatives, traditional lenders and trade union in which government held limited shareholding. The introduction NGO to facilitate the distribution but measures were taken for assurance of repayment by usually village heads for informal borrowers and by the signing of a contract by formal borrowers. In essence, Zimbabwe is also a signatory to the World Trade Organization which requires the opening up of the agricultural sector. The main aim of the liberalization was to create an efficient entrepreneurship in the small-holder agriculture sector with the view to increasing output and ultimately improve food security. The liberalization thus brought about the profit motive in the Zimbabwean agricultural sector thereby making the credit market in agriculture visible from then on. Everyone had an equal chance of obtaining credit. As an example, that was the period when the Marondera District started the production of cash crops such as cotton, paprika, wheat, and sugar cane as the households sought to enhance earnings from agriculture.

In essence, the formation of semi-privatized agricultural marketing entities led to the growth of the credit market in agriculture as most firms introduced contract farming to strengthen their businesses. Some of the companies engaged in agricultural commodities resorted to financing through loans and agricultural credit to small-holder farmers for specified cash crops and grain crops. However, applications were handed in but most farmers did not get these contracts. One such example is the Grain Marketing Board of Zimbabwe which operates an input-credit scheme for the maize farmers. Loans are recovered from the proceeds of the next season's crop. This method of credit financing has proved to be popular, effective and viable and the farmers are in full support of it. Others were said to be getting more than one contract as they were more affiliated to the leaders of these semi-privatized entities.

Musuna and Muchapondwa (2008) postulate that in 2001, the Government of Zimbabwe introduced the crop and livestock input schemes to assist small-holder farmers. Under this arrangement, small-holder farmers were given inputs in the form of loans to be paid back at harvest time through a stop order system administered by the Agricultural Marketing Board. As a result of the agricultural input scheme, the small-holder farmers were able to easily source cheap fertilizers and seeds and that resulted in the achievement of very high productivity but later there were strict requirements for one to obtain credit including gender, age and membership contribution to co-operatives just to mention a few. However, other scholars argue that the loans were susceptible to factors such as social capital because not every small-holder farmer had an equal opportunity to access the credit. Credit is in the form of cash and agricultural inputs. The credit access challenges are vividly pronounced in developing countries than in the developed ones.

On the other hand, since the dollarisation of the economy in 2009, the banking sector has been characterised by short term deposits. This, therefore, explains why the predominantly short term lending is available to agriculture and all other sectors of the economy Malaba, (2014). Bolarinwa and Oyeyinka cited by Ekwere and Edem (2014) observed that inadequate credit provision and poor marketing systems have reduced agricultural production drastically to the extent that food importation has been on the increase in recent years. Against this backdrop, the Government of Zimbabwe (GoZ) and Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs) introduced several initiatives aimed at boosting production to reverse the continuous free fall in maize production. The major theme of these initiatives was centred on the provision of free and subsidized agricultural inputs and machinery mainly targeted at the smallholder farming sector. Although the initiatives

were executed in all the consecutive years since the year 2000, nothing much has been achieved in terms of maize output growth (ZimVac, 2010). The failure to achieve enough maize output for the country following massive government support brings into question whether these inputs were efficiently used in maize production. It also brings to the fore the need to put in place additional and more comprehensive policies that can stimulate maize production so that the country becomes at least food self-sufficient. Evidence from strategic grain reserve (SGR) trends have shown continued decline since 1985, and complete depletion of the reserves by 2008 and the government having to call in private players to help import grain to cover the 2014-2016, El nino related food deficits.

Co-operatives as self-help organisations have been contributing significantly to economic growth and development in terms of empowering poor people and creating an enabling environment to participate actively in economic process in the areas of providing job opportunities, increasing accessibility to credit facilities and increasing social protection but however, they are prone to gender biases. Adefila (2014) noted that the level of educational attainment is crucial to the performance of the farmer co-operatives. It means that efforts should be made geared towards training and re-training of the members in order for them to possess the skills and knowledge required for the organisation to function properly. He adds by saying that it could be achieved through the conduct of seminars, workshops, and conferences where members would be adequately represented and extend such skills to other members.

In a nutshell, other scholars like the Reserve Bank of Zimbabwe (2005) report, notes that the formal financial system provides services to about 35% of the economically active population while the remaining 65% are often excluded from financial services. This is so because of the societal rankings and preferences to high status people. According to the apex financial body, the 65% is often served by the informal sector through NGO-MFIs, friends, relations and credit unions. This then shows the great impact of social capital on credit access

Methodology

The research employed the survey method which used questionnaires as research tools with closed ended questions and a few open ended ones in order to give an in-depth explanation to the closed ended questions.

Research objectives

- To investigate the extent to which strong ties facilitate access to capital to all maize farmers.
- To assess the role that social capital plays in acquiring credit by maize farmers.
- To determine ways to facilitate access to credit to all eligible farmers.

Strong networks (ties) are characterized by an intimate social circle of individual's for instance family members and a close group of friends

Social Capital Variables Description and Measurement

Description of Variables

Variable Name	Description	Expected Sign
Density of membership	This was measured by the number of active household membership in existing associations. A complete inventory of all associations was made at local level institutions; each household was given that inventory and asked which associations they were members of. In other words, the proportion of the membership of associations by individuals was found and rescaled to 100.	Positive
Cash contributions' index	This was achieved by taking records of the payment of membership dues and other contributions. The summation of the total cash contributed to the various associations, which the household belonged to was calculated. The actual contribution for each household was rescaled by dividing the amount by the maximum fee into the data and multiplying the resultant fraction by 100.	Positive
Labour contributions' index	This is the number of days that individual members belonging to the institution claimed to have worked for their institutions. This represents the total numbers of man hour's days worked by household members. This was also rescaled to 100 using the same method of cash contributions.	Positive
NGO Intervention	NGO intervention was chosen as a variable because of its great influence towards access to credit. NGOs try to help people at grass root level revealed by their aims and that greatly showed that smallholder farmers at grass root level need NGO intervention to access credit. But however, they are linked to village heads as these heads provide member names to participate in NGO schemes showing that one should have relations with the village head.	Positive
Gender Household Head	This variable, because of gender inequalities of Gender of the household head will help to distinguish between households headed by males or females. This has an impact on credit as most African countries are patri-lineal which cause disparities in accessing credit because of differences in genders. Males are allowed to have contacts with whoever but females are constrained due to societal norms	Positive
Education Level of the Farmer	Education increases the network and chances for one to access credit. This variable will show firstly the ties of one individual and also how one can use education attained in terms of rights to access credit. Here education shows the bridging type of social capital with its effects on credit access.	Positive
Access to Credit	This will explain if a maize farmer has ever accessed credit before and will also highlight the ways used to obtain credit and the source from which the maize farmer got it.	Dependent Variable

The Measurement of Social Capital

The researcher would employ the General Social Survey (GSS) questions which involve trust, fairness and helping each other. Questions which include participation in social organisations will be included in the questionnaire for they help to measure the degree of effect of social capital. The individual will be asked to indicate the number of organisations one is associated with as a way of establishing one's social tie links.

Trust towards neighbours and people in the area are also going to be used to determine whether if a farmer has strong or weak ties. The researcher would also ask for sources of support actually received previously or these being sought. Questions on the nature of sources will be asked to establish whether they are from formal or informal institutions with the aim of showing the extent of the existence of strong or weak ties and how they influence access to credit. A variety of possible ways will be employed to help in measuring the effect of social capital towards access to credit.

Descriptive statistics

The summary presented help in appreciating the source of variation found in the data. From a sample of 120 households, 113 households responded and this shows a response rate of 94% of the intended sample. This is a high response by any standard.

Table 4:1 Distribution of Households by Access to Credit

Access to Credit	Frequency	Percent
Farmers without access to credit	83	73.45
Farmers with access to credit	30	26.55
Total	113	100

Of the 113 farmers who participated in the research, 83 of them representing 73.45% did not access credit. Only the remaining 30 constituting 26.55% of them benefitted from access to credit.

Figure 4:1 Distribution of Households by Access to Credit

The descriptive statistics results given in Figure 4:1 reveals that the majority of the households sampled for interviews did not benefit from access to credit. This is in line with the existing literature because the empirical evidence suggests that local farmers face challenges relating to eligibility in accessing credit as a result of the reasons emanating from social behaviour and social networks.

Table 4:2 Distributions of the Households by Continuous Variable

Variable	Observation	Mean	Std. Dev.	Minimum	Maximum
Age	113	40	7.6371	30	50
Edu	113	14.159	3.3422	7	20
HSize	113	6	2.4643	2	10

Table 4:2 above shows that the average age of the households was 40 years and the average household size was 6 members. On the other hand, the average educational qualification was advanced level as was measured by the numbers of years an individual spent at school. For instance, an individual would take between 13 and 14 years to attain advanced level qualification depending on whether one attended pre-school or not. Therefore the conclusion drawn from the statistics given above is that the households consist of the mature middle-aged labour force who possess necessary qualifications. The household, because of their high academic achievement, has greater potential for skill training to enhance productivity

Table 4:3 Distributions of the Households by the Gender of Household Head

Gender of the household head	Frequency	Percent
Female	54	47.79
Male	59	52.21
Total	113	100

Table 4:3 shows that out of the 113 households interviewed, 54 were female headed households while 59 were male headed households. This meant that female headed households constituted 47.79% and the male headed

households 52.21%. The results show that in relative terms, male headed households were in the majority although the Zimbabwe population census (2012) indicated that the females constituted 52% of the population. This means that women participation falls far below the expectation.

Table 4:4 Distributions of Households by Strong Networks

Access to Credit	Frequency	Percent
Farmers without access	83	73.45
Farmers with access	30	26.55
Total	113	100

Table 4.4 depicts that out of 113 who answered the questionnaires, 57 households representing 50.44 % had strong networks while 56 of them representing 49.56 % had weak networks.

Figure 4:4 Distributions of Households by Strong Networks

The results showed that the households with strong networks had an advantage over those with weak networks. This was the case because they tended to be linked to the sources of power and had better academic achievements that provided better employment opportunities and the capacity to possess collateral security.

Table 4:5 Distributions of Households by NGO Intervention

NGO intervention	Frequency	Percent
Households helped by NGOs	84	74.34
Households without help from NGOs	29	25.66
Total	113	100

The results show that NGO intervention was high and strong and had 84 households making up 74.34 % of those who reported that they received assistance from NGOs. 29 of the households constituting 25.66 % of the farmers indicated that they did not receive help. The results revealed the NGOs played a pivotal role in assisting women from the lower and poor echelons of the society who could not get assistance from the formal money lending institutions because the society tended to favour men.

Acc	Coef.	Std. Err	Z	P> Z
Gender	0.453887	0.7836496	-1.99	0.047
Age	0.3881158**	0.1946634	1.99	0.046
HSize	0.3420114***	0.1309497	2.61	0.009
Employ	0.0027328*	0.001464	1.87	0.062
Edu	1.677953**	0.7214657	2.33	0.020
MStatus	-0.0043575*	0.0022837	-1.99	0.056
NGOI	0.1558381**	0.7836496	0.44	0.047
MDHA	0.3937375*	0.2156687	1.83	0.068
CCHA	-0.327811***	0.0359976	-11.20	0.010
LCHA	0.6552425	0.118885	7.98	0.000
_cons	-14.97078***	4.845752	-3.09	0.002
Number of obs			113	
LR chi2 (7)			129.97	
Pseudo R ²			0.4335	
Log likelihood			-12.981879	

***Significant at 1% level of significance.

**Significant at 5% level of significance.

*Significant at 10% level of significance

Log Likelihood

This is the log likelihood of the fitted model. It is used in the Likelihood Ratio, Chi-Square test of whether all predictor's regression coefficients in the model used are simultaneously zero. The results show that the model converged and iterations stopped where the Log likelihood was equivalent to -12.981879 which is close to 0. This shows that the model is appropriate for the study.

LR chi2 (7)

This is the likelihood ratio (LR) chi-square test that at least one of the predictor's regression coefficients is not equal to zero. The model has a chi-square statistic of 129.97 with a number in parenthesis indicating the number of degrees of freedom. In this model, there are seven predictors and therefore there are seven degrees of freedom.

Description of results

Social capital indices

Furthermore, the coefficient of membership density of households in associations was positive and statistically significant at 10% level of significance. This showed that an increase in membership of the association by farm households will lead to an increase in the probability of obtaining microcredit. This is due to the fact that when one is a member of different groups then there is a higher chance of one obtaining credit from all of these groups. This result was in conformity with *a priori* expectations. In line with the view of Yusuf (2006), additional membership of farm households in associations increases the probability of access to credit at local level institutions. However, not all people have access to many groups and this will make them more dependent on one source of income and they should be active in these groups for them to obtain this micro-credit.

Households' cash contributions to associations are presumably a sign of greater interest in the associations and serve as a collateral effect for households wanting to borrow money. Contrary to *a priori* expectations, cash contributions of households to associations had a negative coefficient and were highly statistically significant at 1.0% alpha level. This implied that cash contributions made by rural farming households to associations decreased the probability of access to microcredit. It is likely that the farm households at local level institutions in the area of study have not made adequate financial contributions to their institutions due to endemic poverty that reduced their access to credit. This result is not in conformity with Akinyemi *et al* (2012) that obtained a positive relationship between cash contributions and access to microcredit among grain sellers in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria.

The coefficient of labour contributions to associations was significant at 1.0% level of significance. This implied that an increase in man-day labour contributions to associations will increase the probability of obtaining microcredit. It is likely that the local institutions in the study area regard households labour contribution to associations with respect to loan insurance. This result was in tandem with the findings of Ajani and Tijani (2009) who obtained a positive effect of labour contributions on access to microcredit. From the results in Table 4:7, the gender of the household head has an impact on the household's access to credit. The results show a positive relationship between a male headed household and access to credit. The marginal effects results show that being a non-apostolic sect member increases the probability of being insured by 0.7292538.

Other variables

Unexpectedly, the coefficient of primary occupation was positive and significant at 10.0% alpha level. The positive coefficient of this variable indicated that being a farmer increases the probability of obtaining microcredit from local institutions. This may be attributed to the fact that majority of the rural populace in the study area depend entirely on farming and farming activities for survival and generation of income, and as such, they account for the posture of the result. This result contradicted general assumption and the observation of Ajani and Tijani (2009) which stated that being a farmer reduces the chances of accessing microcredit. Also one can note that having other sources of income works as collateral insurance to the borrowers. Also one can note that cash contributions will increase resulting in getting microcredit from these traditional lenders. However, not all farmers have primary occupations leaving most of them vulnerable to shortages of inputs and being in a position of not accessing credit.

The variable, *Edu* was found to positively affect access to credit. The coefficient of this variable was statistically significant at the 0.1 level. The sign of the coefficient shows that there is a positive relationship between the educational level of the household head and access to credit. It could well be said that as people get

more educated, they get better enlightened regarding most aspects pertinent to the benefits and risks associated with borrowing. It may again be the case that as one gets better educated he/she increases the chance of being employed somewhere. Therefore collateral security is usually available as compared to their less educated counterparts. The marginal effects results show that an increase in the education of the household head by one year increases the probability of accessing credit by 0.0017286. However female headed households have a lower probability of accessing credit. This is normal because females, by nature, are at risk averse and they prefer not to borrow.

The coefficient of the *NGOI* variable was statistically significant at 5% level of significance. The results show that NGO Intervention has a positive relationship with access to credit. The marginal results show that an NGO intervention increases the probability of accessing credit by 0.762854. NGO intervention between the government and the people. It tries to bridge the gap that the government cannot by reaching out to the less privileged. However, it works by informing the head of the community of their services and asking for the names of the villagers. By so doing the village head has total control of the villagers who will get assistance. One responded then sighted that they should always do what the village head requires for them to obtain access showing the issue of social relations were one should have strong bonds with the village head going back to the main hypothesis of this study of that social capital positively affects access to credit.

Discussion of Results

The probit regression results show that an increase in membership of the association by farm households will lead to an increase in the probability of obtaining microcredit. This is due to the fact that when one is a member of different groups then there is a higher chance of one obtaining micro-credit from all of these groups. This result was in conformity with *a priori* expectations. In line with the view of Yusuf (2006), additional membership of farm households in associations increases the probability of access to credit at local level institutions. However, not all people have access to many groups and this will make them more dependent on one source of income and they should be active in these groups for them to obtain this micro-credit.

Households' cash contributions to associations are presumably a sign of greater interest in the associations and serve as a collateral effect for households wanting to borrow money. Contrary to *a priori* expectations, cash contributions of households to associations showed to be having a negative impact towards access to credit. This implied that cash contributions made by rural farming households to associations decreased the probability of access to microcredit. It is likely that the farm households at local level institutions in the area of study have not made adequate financial contributions to their institutions due to endemic poverty that reduced their access to credit. This result is not in conformity with Akinyemi *et al* (2012) that obtained a positive relationship between cash contributions and access to microcredit among grain sellers in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria.

The coefficient of labour contributions to associations was significant at 1.0% level of significance. This implied that an increase in man-day labour contributions to associations will increase the probability of obtaining microcredit. It is likely that the local institutions in the study area regard households labour contribution to associations with respect to loan insurance. This result was in tandem with the findings of Ajani and Tijani (2009) who obtained a positive effect of labour contributions on access to microcredit. From the results in Table 4:7, the gender of the household head has an impact on the household's access to credit. The results show a positive relationship between a male headed household and access to credit. The marginal effects results show that being a non-apostolic sect member increases the probability of being insured by 0.7292538.

The variable, Educational level was found to positively affect access to credit. The sign of the coefficient shows that there is a positive relationship between the educational level of the household head and access to credit. It could well be said that as people get more educated, they get better enlightened regarding most aspects pertinent to the benefits and risks associated with borrowing. It may again be the case that as one gets better educated

he/she increases the chance of being employed somewhere. Therefore collateral security is usually available as compared to their less educated counterparts. The descriptive results show that an increase in the education of the household head by one year increases the probability of accessing credit. However female-headed households have a lower probability of accessing credit. This is normal because females, by nature, are at risk averse and they prefer not to borrow.

The NGOi results show that NGO Intervention has a positive relationship with access to credit. NGO intervention between the government and the people. It tries to bridge the gap that the government cannot by reaching out to the less privileged. However, it works by informing the head of the community of their services and asking for the names of the villagers. By so doing the village head has total control of the villagers who will get assistance. One responded then sighted that they should always do what the village head requires for them to obtain access showing the issue of social relations were one should have strong bonds with the village head going back to the main hypothesis of this study of that social capital positively affects access to credit.

Possible innovation

Most Governments have, as part of their macro-economic policy objectives, the desire to realise stable and sustainable economic growth and development as well as increasing the productivity from the resources of the nation. These usually appear to feature as some of the most important policy objectives but their attainment largely depends on the quality of the factors of production of the nation including labour. It thus becomes imperative that as many nationals as possible are guaranteed for food security. Therefore, policymakers interested in improving the living conditions of rural households are advised to consider promoting social capital as one relevant ingredient to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals of Poverty Reduction. It is therefore for this purpose that factors affecting access to credit in the agricultural sector are regarded as intermediate targets in pursuance of the objectives in favour of a healthy labour force needed to spearhead sustainable economic growth and development.

Education was found to be significant because of its positive effect on access to credit, there is a need to craft and implement policies which promote, support and guarantee easy access to education by all. In this regard, however, the Government of Zimbabwean should be commended for playing a significant role in ensuring that education is accessed by the generality of her population but still more needs to be done. It is a fact that the support from various sectors of the economy and the international community who have channelled donor funds towards education should be acknowledged. Of importance, henceforth, should be the agricultural sector development to rid Zimbabwe of intermittent food deficiencies that result in the importation of food grains. This could be possibly achieved through multi-thronged approaches such as encouraging corporate responsibility initiatives towards education and boosting the productive capacity of the nation in agriculture and other sectors of the economy in complementing government efforts. The truth is that the success in agriculture will bring about economic growth, development, and prosperity; something desired by every citizen.

Conclusion

In a nutshell, credit is considered as a catalyst that activates other factors of production and makes under-used capacities functional for increased production. Thus credit plays a significant and pivotal role in agricultural development as it equips farmers to reap economies of scale, venture in fields of production that will be new empowering them to provide utilities for widening their market. The results from the empirical investigation and the probit model show that the factors that influence access to credit among maize small-holder farmers in Marondera District show that the critical and significant social capital variables that influenced access to microcredit were; membership density, cash contributions and labour contributions of households' to associations. Meanwhile, the gender of household head, education level and history of household access to microcredit were the demographic factors that influenced rural household access to microcredit. The study supports findings that in addition to information and other benefits derived from local networks, it can be a

source of obtaining credit. However, belonging to local network or association will improve the probability to access credit for members which can be channeled to activities that would help in improving their livelihood.

Gender of the household head showed that the male headed households have more access to credit institutions due to the fact that Zimbabwe is a patriarchal society with male dominance over everything. However, the equal rights act is rectifying this though females are still disadvantaged. These household headed by males tend to have strong networks through bonding, bridging and linking social ties giving them a higher probability of accessing credit. By the same vein, education is found to have a positive impact on access to credit as also these educated people have social networks through linking social capital were they have access to elites social citizens giving them higher chance to obtain credit.

The regression results revealed that NGO intervention has a significant impact on access to credit. NGO bridges the gap between the government and the people. These organizations help people at a grass-roots level where they involve all farmers with farming schemes, providing basic need as supplements and providing agricultural inputs. An important conclusion drawn from the results is that social capital greatly affects access to credit to farmers.

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